
NIGERIAN MILITARY OPERATIONS UNDER COUNTER-TERRORISM AND ITS BREACH OF HUMAN RIGHT: LEGAL JUSTIFICATION

BY

KENNETH ODHE

Delta State University,
Oleh Campus

&

FAMOUS IZOBO ESQ.

Directorate of General Studies,
Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro

Email: famousono14@yahoo.com

Abstract

In recent times, the debate as to whether the use of force or torture by the Nigerian military forces may be permitted in certain circumstances in Local and International law as a means of extracting and securing life-saving information from terrorist or other criminal elements. This is with a view to preventing unprecedented destructive terrorist threat not only in Nigeria but in sub-Sahara Africa and beyond is gaining momentum. In several occasions, the Nigerian security forces are confronted with the issue of justifying the use of physical persuasive tactics in order to obtain vital information from terrorist such as Boko Haran, ISWAP, bandits and others. This sometimes contravenes the basic principles of human right in the criminal justice system, wherein an accused is deemed innocent until proven guilty by a competent court of jurisdiction as well as other constitutionally guaranteed rights. On 23rd day of March 2022, the Abuja-Kaduna train was bombed by bandit-terrorist, killing eight persons while many were injured and over 60 persons kidnapped in Nigeria. The correctional facility for inmates at Kuje was attacked by ISWAP on 5th July 2022 and over 600 prison inmates escaped, including about 60 Boko haram fighters still at large till date. No doubt the primary responsibility of the State is to ensure the safety and security of lives and property, while the use of torture is absolutely prohibited under Local and International Law. Supposing the Nigerian military forces are aware of the Abuja-Kaduna terrorist bomb would go off in an undisclosed public place, and it may be impossible to get people out in time, to what extent can security personnel be permitted to resort to the use of physical force as a means of obtaining necessary important information as to the location of the bomb from the terrorist suspects before it goes off?. Again, what is the legal justification of temporarily legalizing a crime in order to prevent another likely bigger crime under International Law? Should the law be used to sacrifice a few in hopes that it would prevent harm to the majority? One way of tackling this dilemma may be to distinguish between the justification of the use of torture and culpability of the torturer. Therefore, the fact that torture was used as means of preventing a threat may not necessarily excuse the crime of the torture even though in matters of National security, there is always a waiver of the rule of law.

Keywords: Nigerian Military, Counter-Terrorism, Human Rights, Legal Justification

Introduction

When National security is an issue, there is always a waiver of the rule of law.¹

It is important for the military forces to continuously strike a balance between the protection of human rights and the need to ensure the security of lives and property, otherwise it risk impeding rights it seeks to protect in the first place.² The variations in defining the crime of terrorism and by extension, who qualifies as a terrorist also make it difficult to prosecute the global war against the crime while cautiously protecting against any violation of human rights.³ This article examines the issues associated with human rights protection and combating terrorism in three fold; first, the urgent and absolute necessity of fighting terrorism in all its ramifications. Secondly, the need to respect human rights and not violate them, that is, upholding the universal tenets that every accused person is innocent until proven guilty. Thirdly, the proposition that despite the measures that are much needed to counter terrorism, human rights should never be violated, that is, balancing the need for counter-terrorism against protection of human rights. The human rights discussed in this article are wide enough to cover the act of terrorism as a violation of human rights, the rights of the alleged perpetrators as well as the actions taken by the Military forces to counter or prevent terror.

In Nigeria, Boko Haram started as Islamic sectarian movement in 2002, led by Muhammed Yusuf in Borno State of Northern Nigeria.⁴ Boko Haram is interpreted in Hausa language to mean “Western education is a forbidden” as it is perceived to be a major influence of corruption and bad governance in Nigeria. The terrorist group faced a worldwide condemnation after kidnapping more than 275 girls from boarding school in Chibok in Borno State in April 2013 in the Northeast.⁵ The group was officially declared a terrorist group by former President Goodluck Jonathan in June 2013 and was banned under the Nigeria Law (Terrorism Prevention Act). In same year, the United Nation Security Council imposed sanctions on individuals in Boko Haram, freezing assets and issuing travel bans and arms embargo. However, the sanctions could not achieve much desire result due to the informal structure of the group. After Yusuf’s death, the group started splitting into multiple factions, with the main faction being led by Shekau who served as Yusuf’s deputy. Shekau vowed to avenge Yusuf’s death and later had a link with other terrorist network such as al-Qaeda. In March 2015, the group pledged allegiance to (ISIL) an insurgent group in Iraq and Syria and took the name (ISWAP) which was later known as (ISWA). These set of terrorist broke into different factions which were collectively referred to in Hausa as Boko Haram.⁶ A group that carried out major destructive and offensive attack on Nigerians, such as the killing of 50 male students and destruction of college in Yobe State in 2013, kidnapping of more than 275 girls from boarding school in Chibok in Borno State in April 2013, attack on prison in Bauchi State to release 700 inmates and 100 Boko Haram members in 2010. In August 26th 2011, the group also struck the international target with Nigeria suicide bombers with a car that crashed into the United Nation building killing about 23 people and 100 injured, the list of attack by this group on innocent Nigerians is countless.

¹ Major Gen. Babagana Mogoun (Rtd); Former National Security Adviser to the President of Federal Republic of Nigeria

² Szurlej Christina. (2011). “Protecting Human Rights while Countering Terrorism a Decade after 9/11”. *Essex Human Rights Review* 2.

³ *Ibid*

⁴ www.britannica.com

⁵ *Ibid*

⁶ *Ibid*

Furthermore, bandit is another concept that has metamorphosed into terrorism in Nigeria. The origin of bandit conflict can be traced back to herder – former conflicts that plague Nigeria.⁷ It is an assortment of the various criminal groups involved in extensive cattle rustling, sexual violence, kidnapping, armed robbery, pillage and attacks on gold mineral and traders particularly in North-West Nigeria.⁸ As a result of its violent crimes such as the Abuja-Kaduna train bomb on 23rd March 2022, where 8 persons died, many persons injured and over 60 persons kidnapped in Nigeria. In the same vein, on the 5th of July 2022, the correctional facility for inmates at Kuje was attacked by ISWAP, where over 600 prison inmates escaped, including about 60 Boko Haram fighters still at large till date in Nigeria. In spite of the fact that the Federal Government tried to play politics with situations, the court took a bold step when it declared bandits as terrorists in Nigeria.⁹ A month later, the federal government of Nigeria did the same and declares bandits a terrorist group.¹⁰ The declaration titled, Terrorism (Prevention) Proscription Order Notice, 2021 as contained in volume 108 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette.

The fight which appears to be seen as one against ideology rather than a known group of persons is of little or no success. The variations in the deformation of the enemy have made it difficult to fight against an ideology rather than to a known group of persons.¹¹ Further, the variations in the definition of the enemy have made it difficult to successfully prosecute the war. Several conventions, declarations and resolutions have made attempts to define both the act of terrorism as well as who qualifies as a terrorist. According to the United Nations Assembly Resolution on Measures to Eliminate International Terrorism on December 1994, para.1-3, the resolutions stipulate that:

- (1) The States Members of the United Nations solemnly reaffirm their unequivocal condemnation of all acts, methods and practices of terrorism, as criminal and unjustifiable, wherever and by whomever committed, including those which jeopardize the friendly relations among States and peoples or threaten the territorial integrity and security of States;
- (2) Acts, methods and practices of terrorism constitute a grave violation of the purposes and principles of the United Nations, which may pose a threat to international peace and security, jeopardize friendly relations among States, hinder international cooperation and aim at the destruction of human rights, fundamental freedoms and the democratic bases of society;
- (3) Criminal acts intended or calculated to provoke a state of terror in the general public, a group of persons or particular persons for political purposes are in any circumstance unjustifiable, whatever the considerations of a political, philosophical, ideological, racial, ethnic, religious or any other nature that may be invoked to justify them.¹²

Furthermore, on 26th January 1999, United Nations General Assembly Resolution 53/108 on measures to eliminate terrorism reiterated that criminal acts intended or calculated to provoke a state of terror in the general public, a group of persons or particular persons for political purposes are in any circumstances unjustifiable, whatever the considerations of a political,

⁷ Nigeria bandit conflict – wikipedia available at [en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki-Nigeria](http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nigeria)

⁸ www.cambridge.org core article

⁹ Ikechukwu Nnochiri. (2021). "Court declare bandit terrorist". *Vanguard News*. 26th November. available at www.vanguardngr.com news

¹⁰ Ameh Ochojila: At last, Federal Government declare bandit as terrorist. *The Guardian Nigeria* 6th January 2022.

¹¹ Szurlej Christina, 'Protecting Human Rights while Countering Terrorism a Decade after 9/11' [2011]2

¹² Available at <http://www.un.org/documents/ga/res/49/a49r060.htm> accessed 12th November 2022.

philosophical, ideological, racial, ethnic, religious or other nature that may be invoked to justify them.¹³ It is therefore obvious that the activities of bandits, ISWAP and Boko Haram in Nigeria popularly fit into what the United Nations stand to fight against. However, the failure to proffer a universally accepted definition has not only made it difficult to successfully wage war against terrorism but to also deal with, and effectively prosecute those alleged to have committed crimes of terror. While there is a need to adopt measures that adequately prevent terror attacks, there is also a need to ensure that these measures do not in themselves violate the human rights they seek to protect. It has been noted that government must take steps to meet its human rights obligations to its citizens by ensuring that counter terrorism measures do not violate international human rights, humanitarian and refugee law.¹⁴ Some of these actions which are adopted by the State as counter terrorism measures but which have been reputed as violations of human rights and dignity include unlawful arrests and prolonged or indefinite detentions, referring civilians to military or exceptional state security courts, prohibiting the press, demonstrations and public meetings, among others.¹⁵ It is noted that many countries violate human rights in the name of countering terrorism. Their definition of terrorism is sometimes self-serving and based on their political interest.¹⁶ The absence of a uniform definition of terrorism leads to misuse and an overly wide application of counter terrorism measures, often used in suppressing those who merely dissent from social or political norms of the society.¹⁷ Yet in certain situations, it may be difficult to reconcile the protection of human right and dignity against the preservation of security of lives and property. For example, in the Abuja-Kaduna train bomb, if the State is in custody of an individual alleged to be involved with the intended bomb attack set to go off at an undisclosed location at an unknown time, it may be difficult to reconcile the extent to which the State be permitted to truncate the human rights of the individual in order to secure vital information that may prevent the death of a large population.¹⁸ On the one hand, the State has the responsibility of securing the lives of its citizens, while in Nigeria every individual is entitled to right to privacy, fair hearing as well as freedom from torture and other dehumanizing treatment which are sometimes employed in these types of situations. The State must therefore find a way of protecting citizens from terrorist attacks and not engage in or condone any act that is capable of violating the rights of the citizens. This has been a major concern of the United Nations human rights programme, which places a priority on protection of the rights of individual viz-a-viz implementing counter terrorism measures.¹⁹

What could be the justification for the breach of Human Right in Nigeria by the Military forces under counter-terrorism operations?

Terrorism has been described as a creeping threat that is aimed directly at the heart of democratic institutions.²⁰ Globally, it has constituted a challenge not only the United Nations but also regional and domestic authorities by threatening international peace and security.²¹

¹³ Available at <http://daccessdds.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N99/762/67/PDF/N9976267.pdf?OpenElement> accessed 12th November, 2022.

¹⁴ Wilkinson P., *Terrorism and the Liberal State* (New York University Press 1979).

¹⁵ Human rights Watch in the name of counter terrorism: *Human Rights abuses worldwide, a paper for the 59th session of the United Nations Commission on Human Rights* (2003)

¹⁶ Ayoub A., 'Terrorism Prevention and Human Rights Violation' [2012] *Asian Transactions on Basic and Applied Sciences* 33.

¹⁷ Szurlej Christina, 'Protecting Human Rights while Countering Terrorism a Decade after 9/11' [2011]2

¹⁸ Langfur S. Answer to the judge: The ticking bomb and the license to torture [1996].

<http://www.hartfordlaw.com/archives/51a/095.html> accessed 12th November, 2022.

¹⁹ Ayoub A., 'Terrorism Prevention and Human Right Violation' [2012]31

²⁰ Chalk P., *West European Terrorism and Counter Terrorism: The Evolving Dynamic* (Macmillan 1996).

²¹ Arabamen O.A. and others 'The impact of Counter-Terrorism Laws on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms' [2015]3 *Akunga Law Journal*, 131

Since the 9/11 attacks in the United States of America, several terrorist events have taken place in Nigeria and other jurisdictions. The recent one in Nigeria include the Abuja-Kaduna bomb attack on 23rd day of March 2022 and the Kuje prison break on 5th July 2022, similarly, the Al-Qaeda Islamic terrorists led a campaign of brutal violence across northern Mali in their bid to impose sharia and hudud punishments. This led to the amputation and death of several innocent persons.²² Despite the devastating effects of terrorism on the international community, there has been a lack of consensus on the definition of terrorism and this has made it difficult not only to identify offenders but to also garner international support in engaging counter terrorism measures.²³ A globally accepted definition of terrorism would also help to structure rules of engagement for dealing with potentials terrorist, gathering evidence and successful prosecution.

In order to ensure peace and security, the Nigeria Military has often had to engage in several counter terrorism measures. Counter-terrorism refers to the practices, tactics, techniques that governments all over the world adopt in order to prevent or respond to terrorist threats or attacks. These measures include offensive strategies aimed at preventing a belligerent, in a broader conflict from successfully using tactics of terrorism. Counter-terrorism measures are usually adopted to prevent, deter, preempt and respond to terrorism.²⁴ To this end, there are several international, regional and domestic legislation adopted to prevent terrorist attacks.²⁵ Similarly, Nigeria have often engaged in certain acts which, though aimed at preventing or combating terrorism, threaten the fundamental human rights of individuals. It has been noted that anti-terrorism legislations often have the potential to condone abuse of human rights.²⁶ For example, the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1267 which was adopted under Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter which Nigeria is a member created the Al-Qaeda and Taliban Sanctions Committee. This committee has power to impose measures which apply to designated individuals and entities associated with Al-Qaeda wherever they may be. This is done through the creation of a list of these individuals. Once a person or an organization's name is put on the list (usually through the initiative of a member of the Security Council and a swift approval by other members), all States are obliged to freeze the assets of the individual and restrict his movement. It has been argued that this power gives the Security Council a quasi-judicial role, while its procedures continue to fall short of international human rights treaties and customary international law fundamental principles of right to fair hearing for the individuals who find their names on the list of terrorists.²⁷ Similarly, there are various arguments, doctrines and constructions that seek to justify unilateral exceptions to human rights norms in the fight against terrorism. It has been noted that many of these constructions have a valid legal basis as well as a proper scope of application. They include:²⁸

²² Global Terrorism Database: Information on over 113,000 Terrorist attacks <http://www.terrorim-research.com/> accessed 12th November, 2022.

²³ Netanyahu B., (Ed.) *International Terrorism: Challenge and Response* Jerusalem: (The Jonathan Institute 1980) 47

²⁴ Arabamen, O.A and others 'The impact of Counter-Terrorism Laws on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms' [2015] 137

²⁵ For example, United Nations Convention on the making of plastic explosives, OAU Convention on the prevention and combating of Terrorism, 1999, International Convention for the Suppression of Terrorist Bombing 1998.

²⁶ Arabamen, O.A and others 'The impact of Counter-Terrorism Laws on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms' [2015] 135

²⁷ Ginsborg Lisa and Scheinini Martin 'You can't always get what you want: The Kadi II Conundrum and the Security Council 1267 Terrorist Sanctions Regime' [2011] 8 (1) *Essex Human Rights Review* 7

²⁸ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilaterla Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to deny or reduce the applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fights against Terrorism' [2010] *European University Institute Working Papers*

- i. The States' denial of individuals their status as protected persons under international humanitarian law.
- ii. The United Nations Charter as *lex superior* compared to human rights obligations.
- iii. Denial of attribution to an individual state of action by inter-governmental organizations
- iv. Denial of extraterritorial nature of human rights
- v. Upholding reservations to human rights treaties
- vi. Persistent objection to norms of customary international law
- vii. Derogation during times of emergency

1. The States' denial of individuals' status as protected persons under international humanitarian law

In contrast with international humanitarian law,²⁹ human rights are innate. They are the basic irreducible minimum requirement for a civilized society which all humans are entitled to by virtue of their humanity.³⁰ International humanitarian law was developed from the need to ensure that specific groups of people are protected, since they are not the legitimate targets of lethal force during armed conflict.³¹ These categories of persons include the wounded, sick, shipwrecked members of the armed forces at sea, prisoners of war and civilians.

It should be noted that after the 9/11 attacks, the United States of America sought to limit the rights enjoyed by individuals under humanitarian law by arguing that suspected terrorists do not fall within the categories of protected persons under international humanitarian law. According to the Bush administration, the suspected terrorists were neither combatants nor civilians. They were therefore categorized as 'unlawful alien enemy combatants' who, according to the Bush administration, were entitled to be detained indefinitely without trial and without prisoner of war status.³² This argument formed the basis for denying human rights to persons detained in Guantanamo Bay as the United States could not be held accountable for the breach of the human rights. It is however worthy of note that the United States is a signatory to the Geneva Conventions as well as the ICCPR and is obligated under the Conventions to ensure protection from torture and other cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment and same applies to Nigeria bandit and Boko Haram. Furthermore, it has been noted that the notion of 'unlawful combatant' is merely an expression employed by the United States for convenience and not one that carries any legal consequences.³³ Note that before the court declare bandit as terrorist, President Buhari used to refer bandits as mere criminal element and should not be treated as terrorist.

²⁹ International humanitarian law is encapsulated in the Geneva Conventions. Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field, Article 2, Aug. 12, 1949, 75 United Nations Treaty Series 31; Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea, Article 2, Aug. 12, 1949, 75 United Nations Treaty Series 85; Geneva convention relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War, Article 2, Aug. 12 1949, 75 United Nations Treaty Series 135, and Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian persons in Time of War, Article 2, Aug. 12, 1949, 75 United Nations Treaty Series 287. Additional Protocol 1 is also applicable to international armed conflicts, however, the United has not ratified it. See, States parties to Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protections of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol1)/

³⁰ An-Naim A., *Universal Rights Local Remedies* (Interights, Afronet, GTZ, 1997) 7

³¹ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that Seek to Deny or Reduce the applicability of Human Rights Norms in the fight against Terrorism

³² Ibid

³³ Moser P.T. 'Torture Papers, Never Again-Guarantees of Non-repetition for the Torture Committed by the Bush Administration during the 'War on Terror' [2011] 8 (1) *Essex Human Rights Review* <http://projects.essex.ac.uk/ehrr/vol8no1.html> accessed 22nd November, 2022.

2. The United Nations Charter as *lex superior* compared to human rights obligations

Another method employed by States to limit the application of human rights norms in the prosecution of counter terrorism measures is the argument that the techniques and measures adopted by them are those under which they have an obligation to employ by virtue of the United Nations Charter and its Chapter VII on the Security Council's power to impose mandatory measures on its members in bid to secure international peace and security. Article 103 of the UN charter provides that the Charter supersedes all other treaty obligations, including those bordering on human rights.³⁴ This is designed to ensure concerted global efforts that are coordinated to rid the world of terror and to prevent any hindrance with regards to obligations created under other treaties. It is however argued that there is no contradiction between human rights and the UN Charter as the protection of human rights is one of the focal points of the United Nations.³⁵ Further the functions and powers of the United Nations Security Council are to be exercised in accordance with this purpose.³⁶

It has been noted that even where States are obliged under Chapter VII to undertake certain counter terrorism measures, these measures must be implemented in full compliance with human rights norms. There is nothing in Chapter VII that makes it mandatory for States to deviate from their own human rights norms in a bid to implement counter terrorism measures.³⁷ The Nigeria military forces are no exception in the applicability of chapter VII of UN Charter in fighting bandits and Boko Haram.

3. States denial of actions taken by its agencies or by intergovernmental organizations

In certain situations where a State is involved in international administration of a territory, where a State is required under its international obligations to send its troops for peace keeping missions or to participate as part of international forces, the State may seek to rely on the primary of its UN Charter obligations, extraterritorial nature of their actions and by arguing that the action in question be attributed to the international organization in order to avoid liability for acts committed by its troops.

In *Behrami and Behrami v. France*³⁸ the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) accepted the argument that individual States could not be held liable for the acts and omissions of its contingent forces which were directly attributable to the United Nations. Similarly, in *Ilaz Kasumaj v. Greece*³⁹ and *Slavisa v. Germany*⁴⁰ the ECHR relied on the *Behrami* case in declaring inadmissible several complaints bordering on the actions of states who were acting on behalf of the United Nations, such as those who participated as part of KFOR in Kosovo.⁴¹

Be that as it may, it should however be noted that these decisions have been heavily criticized on the basis that it is legally possible for both the international organization and the

³⁴ Kelsen H. 'Conflicts between Obligations under the Charter of the United Nations and Obligations under other International Agreements – An Analysis of Article 103 of the Charter (2008) 10 *Univ of Pittsburg Law Review* 284

³⁵ Art 1 United Nations Charter

³⁶ Art 25, para 2 United Nations Charter

³⁷ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that Seek to Deny or Reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the fight against Terrorism' [2010] 10

³⁸ Application no. 71412/01

³⁹ (2007) Application no. 6974/05

⁴⁰ (2007) Application no. 31446/02

⁴¹ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 14

individual State to be held liable for acts that violate human rights of individuals. Therefore the fact that the negative effect of the actions taken is attributable to the international organization does not preclude liability from being shared by the individual State.⁴² The Human Rights Committee has consistently held that States remain liable whenever members of their national contingent participating in international forces abroad commit acts that are a violation of human rights norms. According to the Committee, ‘this principle also applies to those within the power or effective control of the forces of a State Party acting outside its territory, regardless of the circumstances in which such power or effective control was obtained, such as forces constituting a national contingent of a State Party assigned to an international peace-keeping or peace-enforcement operation’.⁴³ In *R (on the application of Al-Jedda) v Secretary of State for Defence*⁴⁴ the appellant had not been charged with any offence, and no charge or trial was. He was however arrested and detained on the ground that his detention was necessary in the interest of the national security of Iraq. The appellant was suspected of being a member of a terrorist group involved in weapons smuggling and explosive attacks in Iraq. He was believed by the British authorities to have been personally responsible for recruiting terrorists outside Iraq with a view to the commission of atrocities, facilitating the travel into Iraq of an identified terrorist explosives expert, among other allegations. He however denied these allegations and they did not form the basis of any legal proceedings against the appellant. Nor was their correctness an issue in the appeal proceedings. The House of Lords had to determine the legal issues without forming any judgment whether they were true or not. The legal issues put before the Court by the Respondent was whether the provisions of article 5(1) of the European Convention on Human Rights were qualified by the legal regime established pursuant to the United Nations Security Council Resolution (“UNSCR”) 1546 (and subsequent resolutions) by reasons of the operation of articles 25 and 103 of the UN Charter, such that the detention of the appellant had not been in violation of article 5(1). The Secretary of State, relying strongly on the *Behrami case*, argued that the appellant’s detention ought to be attributable to the United Nations in these circumstances. The House of Lords in distinguishing between the MNF in Iraq and the KFOR in Kosovo held that the United Nations could not be held liable for the appellant’s detention.

4. Denial of extraterritorial nature of human rights

Another argument adopted in support of the unilateral exceptions to human rights norms in the fight against terrorism is that human rights are territorial in nature i.e. they are limited to the territory in which the State has jurisdiction. Therefore the State cannot be required to respect the human rights of individuals in territories over which it has no jurisdiction.⁴⁵ This argument is employed where States establish detention centres abroad such as Guantanamo Bay, and argue that constitutionally guaranteed rights do not apply there. Such States also rely on the wording of Article 2(1) ICCPR that states that ‘Each State Party to the present Covenant undertakes to respect and to ensure to all individuals within its territory and subject to its jurisdiction the rights recognized in the present Covenant.’⁴⁶

It has been noted that the reference to ‘jurisdiction’ with respect to the relationship between an individual as beneficiary of a human right and the State as the party charged with ensuring

⁴² Ibid

⁴³ See HRC General Comment 31 (2008)1 HRI/GEN/1/Rev. 9 para 10

⁴⁴ [2007] UKHL 58

⁴⁵ Denis M. ‘Application of Human Rights Treaties Extraterritorially in times of armed conflict and military occupation’ [2005] 99 AJIL 119

⁴⁶ Art 2(1) ICCPR

such rights are respected, is with regards to the degree of control or responsibility over the circumstances that affect the enjoyment of human rights by the individual in question.⁴⁷ Therefore it is argued by some authors that in order to be held accountable for human rights violations, the State must be in effective control of the territory.⁴⁸ It is important to note however, that this argument on the territorial nature of human rights has no bearing as human rights treaties are not limited to territory or jurisdiction or jurisdiction of a State but have a wider international scope. Customary international law is broad enough to impugn liability on a State that violates human rights through its agents outside its territory.

5. Upholding Reservations to Human Rights Treaties

States sometimes take reservations to specific areas of treaties to which they intend to be bound, in order to bring it in conformity with their domestic law and to limit the legal applicability of those aspects of the treaty to the individual State. The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties defines reservation as a unilateral statement, however phrased or named, made by a State, when signing, ratifying, accepting, approving or acceding to a treaty, whereby it purports to exclude or to modify the legal effect of certain provision of the treaty in their application to that State.⁴⁹ The circumstances under which a State may not be permitted to take reservations include:⁵⁰

- a. the reservation is prohibited by the treaty.
- b. The treaty provides that only specified reservations, which do not include the reservation in questions, may be made; or
- c. in cases not falling under sub-paragraphs (a) and (b), the reservation is incompatible with the object and purpose of the treaty.

Generally, reservations are very controversial in international law. For example, in 1986 the United States had taken to reservations to the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide:⁵¹

- i. That any case to which the United States is a party cannot be submitted to the International Court of Justice without specific consent from the US.
- ii. That the United States reserves the right to decide whether, when and how the Convention on Genocide can be applied to itself.

These reservations were strongly criticized by other nations who saw the move by US as an abrogation of the United States commitment to the Convention. Denmark, Finland and Greece protested the US reservation as invalid under international law.⁵²

It is good to state that while international law prohibits reservations that run afoul of the intent and purpose of the treaty, there are certain human rights treaties that do not permit

⁴⁷ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 16

⁴⁸ Scheinin M, 'Extraterritorial Effect of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights' in Coomans F. and Kamminga M. (eds), *Extraterritorial Application of Human Rights Treaties* (Intersentia 2004) 73-81

⁴⁹ Art. 2 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969.

⁵⁰ Art. 19 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969

⁵¹ Declarations and Reservations to the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide 1948 https://www.icrc.org/eng/assets/files/other/irrc_849_gaudreau-eng.pdf accessed 25th November, 2022.

⁵² Gerald J.B., 'Is the U.S Really a signatory to the U.N Convention on Genocide?' <http://www.serendipity.li/more/genocide.html> accessed 25th November 2022

reservations while others limit the scope of any possible reservations.⁵³ Human rights treaties often establish tribunals that help to monitor and make decisions with regards to the implementation of the treaty. This has helped to ensure the bindingness of human rights treaties. It is however interesting to note that no reservations have been entered with respect to human rights treaties in relation to terrorism.⁵⁴ Whenever such reservations arise they must be in conformity with the object and purpose of the human rights convention, or otherwise deemed of no legal consequence.

6. Persistent Objection to Norms of Customary International Law

Another technique employed by Nigeria Military force that seek to justify its breach of human rights norms in the fight against terrorism is by dissociating themselves from norms of customary international law.⁵⁵ Customary international law refers to State practice that is widely accepted by the State as obligatory.⁵⁶ States that seek to limit the applicability of those customary norms that regard human rights as paramount, especially in time of conflict, do so by opposing the adoption of declarations or resolutions of the United Nations that set these human rights norms as binding on the international community.⁵⁷ The persistent objector rule international provides an escape hatch for states that do not wish to be bound by a newly emerging norm of customary persistently object during its formation.⁵⁸ Hence the former National Security Adviser to the President, (Mongonu Babagana) once said that when the security of a nation is in issue, there is a waiver of the rule of law in military operations. States however cannot object to those norms that have attained the level of *jus cogens*.⁵⁹

7. Derogation during times of emergency

Derogation from human rights norms is considered the most far-reaching of the permissible techniques for unilateral modification of a State's legal obligations.⁶⁰ Such derogations occur when specific circumstances make it difficult for the State to fully comply with its expected obligations under both international and domestic human rights laws. In such circumstances there has to exist an emergency which threatens the life of the nation and a state of emergency must have been declared by the relevant authority.⁶¹ Treaties also sometimes have derogation clauses. For example, Article 4 of the ICCPR provides that

In time of public emergency which threatens the life of the nation and the existence of which is officially proclaimed, the States Parties to the present Covenant may take measures derogating from their obligations under the present Covenant to the extent strictly required by the exigencies of the situation, provided that such measures are not inconsistent with their other obligations under international law and

⁵³ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 18

⁵⁴ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 19

⁵⁵ Ibid

⁵⁶ See Art. 38(1) (b) of ICJ

⁵⁷ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 20

⁵⁸ Chin Leng Lim and Elias O. "Withdrawing from custom and the paradox of consensualism in international law' [2010] 21 *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law* 143-156

⁵⁹ Lau H. 'Rethinking the persistent objector doctrine in international human rights law' [2005]6 *Chicago Journal of International Law* 495

⁶⁰ Hartman J. 'Derogation from Human rights treaties in public emergencies [1981] 1 *Harvard International Law Journal* 2

⁶¹ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 21

do not involve discrimination solely on the ground of race, colour, sex, language, religion or social origin.⁶²

On the other hand there are treaties that border on human rights of specific individuals which do not make provision for any derogation. For example, the Covenant on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities makes provision for a special clause which creates an obligation on States not to derogate even in times of emergency.⁶³ It has been noted that the major criterion for the validation of a State's derogations is the existence of an emergency which threatens the life of the State.⁶⁴ Therefore, a threat such as a terrorist attack or a situation in which a terrorist organization manages to disrupt public peace and order would qualify as a 'threat to the life of a nation' and necessitate derogations from human rights norms for a limited time.⁶⁵ For example, the State may declare a curfew during a state of emergency in its efforts to maintain public peace, safety and security as was done in some part of the North-east of Nigeria in 2004.

While International law⁶⁶ provides for the principle of strict proportionality wherein the State is entitled to take measures which effectively derogate from its legal obligations in a time of emergency, it is however limited to "the extent strictly required by the exigencies of the situation, and provided that the State provide remedies for any violation of these rights."⁶⁷ Similarly, restriction and derogation from fundamental rights are also contained in the Nigerian constitution.⁶⁸ The Constitution allows the National Assembly to make laws that limit the rights of Nigerian citizens, subject to certain conditions. The State must however ensure that the measures adopted in derogating from its obligations to uphold human rights norms must be proportional to the threat or emergency being faced. In *William v Majekodunmi*⁶⁹ it was held that the restriction order on the Legal Adviser of the Action Group was not reasonably justifiable by the Emergency. The Court however noted that whether a state of emergency existed was a matter for the parliament to decide. As such, the court is therefore not entitled to look beyond the provisions of the constitution in determining whether or not the state of emergency declared by the parliament is valid.⁷⁰

However, in Europe, the European Court of Human Rights has the duty of ascertaining whether a State has acted proportionately in response to a public emergency. This is despite the wide powers given to parliament.⁷¹ In *Lawless v Ireland*⁷² the Court held that it could assess the government's appraisal of the given situation in order to determine whether the use of emergency powers was justified. In the same vein, the United Nations' Human Rights Committee has reiterated that measures adopted by a State which derogate from the provisions of the ICCPR must be of 'an exceptional and temporary nature'. The writer make bold to state that what constitute an exceptional nature for the Nigeria military forces in

⁶² See also Article 15 ECHR

⁶³ Article 11 CRPD

⁶⁴ Mokhtar A. 'Human rights obligations v. derogations: article 15 of the European convention on human rights' [2004]8 *International Journal of Human Rights* 67

⁶⁵ Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International Law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that seek to Deny or reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the Fight against Terrorism' [2010] 22

⁶⁶ See Article 4(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and Article 15(1) of the European Convention on Human Rights.

⁶⁷ Article 2(3) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights

⁶⁸ Section 45 CFRN, 1999

⁶⁹ (1962) ALL NLR 413

⁷⁰ See also *Adegbenro v. A.G Federation* (1962) WNL150R

⁷¹ Akinseye-George, Y. *Improving Judicial Protection of Human Rights in Nigeria* (Abuja: Centre for Socio-Legal Studies (2011) p. 356

⁷² (1961)1 EHRR 15

operation must be treated with caution and be seen in the eyes of a reasonable man to be exceptional in nature.

Appreciating Human Rights in the context of counter-terrorism

Since post 9/11, governments have made efforts to engage in legal argumentation in a bid to justify counter terrorism measures that amount to internationally wrongful acts, or more specifically, acts that amount to human rights violations.⁷³ For example, some of the techniques used by the United States military forces under the President George W. Bush administration in interrogating suspected terrorists as part of the ‘enhanced interrogation’ techniques include sleep deprivation, water boarding, violent shaking, sexual humiliation, stress positions, beating and temperature manipulations. However, the administration considered these enhanced interrogation techniques to be aggressive, yet lawful.⁷⁴ These techniques were adopted despite the international human rights law guaranteed freedom from torture, inhuman and degrading treatment or punishment.⁷⁵ Why then is it an issue when the Nigerian military forces adopt and follow same in fighting bandit and Boko Haram in Nigeria?

In arguing for its use of ‘enhanced interrogation’ techniques, the United States military forces relied on a set of memorandums written by governmental lawyers from different State agencies. These memorandums are commonly referred to as the ‘Torture Papers’.⁷⁶ While the U.S Statute 18 United States Code 2340 2340A (hereinafter referred to as the Torture Act) defines torture as ‘an act committed by a person acting under the colour of law specifically intended to inflict severe physical or mental pain or suffering (other than pain incidental to lawful sanctions) upon another person within his custody or physical control’,⁷⁷ the Torture Papers concluded that for an act to amount to torture, the severe pain caused must rise to ‘the level that would ordinarily be associated with a sufficiently serious physical condition or injury such as death, organ failure, or serious impairment of body functions’.⁷⁸ According to the lawyers therefore, these interrogation techniques employed by the US government did not meet the severity requirement for torture, and as such their continued use did not violate the US Torture Act. President Donald Trump has also stated that he believes in the use of torture and would consider reinstating water boarding as an interrogation method because “we have to fight fire with fire.”⁷⁹ The International Court of Justice has however affirmed that States must:

adhere strictly to the rule of law, including the core principles of criminal and inter-national law and the specific standards and obligations of international human rights law, refugee law and, where applicable, humanitarian law. These principles, standards and obligations define the boundaries of permissible and legitimate state action against terrorism. The

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ Moser P.T ‘Torture Papers, Never Again-Guarantees of Non-repetition for the Torture Committed by the Bush Administration during the ‘War on Terror’ [2011]

⁷⁵ Art. 7 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1976

⁷⁶ Moser P.T ‘Torture Papers, Never Again-Guarantees of Non-repetition for the Torture Committed by the Bush Administration during the ‘War on Terror’ [2011] 8, 201

⁷⁷ 18 United States Code 2340 (1) (2004)

⁷⁸ Memorandum from Jay S. Bybee, Assistant Attorney Gen., Office of Legal Counsel, U.S. Dept. of Justice, to Alberto R. Gonzales, Counsel to the president, Standards of Conduct for Interrogation under 18 United States Code 2340-A (Agu. 1, 2022) reprinted in the Torture Papers.

⁷⁹ Irish Examiner ‘Trump endorses Torture: Principe or Pragmatism?’ <http://www.irishexaminer.com/viewpoints/ourview/trump-endorses-torture-principle-or-pragmatism-440973.html> accessed 25th November 2022.

odious nature of terrorist acts cannot serve as a basis or pretext for states to disregard their international obligations, in particular in the protection of fundamental human rights.⁸⁰

Examining State's justification for the use of Torture in counter terrorism in foreign Jurisdiction

The Israeli ticking time bomb case in retrospect⁸¹ may serve as model case to test whether the use of torture may be permitted in certain cases as a means of obtaining vital information that may prevent terrorist attacks or threats. These cases relate to how detainees should be treated, as prescribed under international humanitarian law and human rights law. In the Israeli ticking bomb case the Israeli Commission of Inquiry had recommended that the use of means of pressure was necessary and effective in the interrogation of terrorist suspects in order to overcome the obdurate will not to disclose information and to overcome the fear of the terrorist that he may be harmed for divulging such information.⁸² Similarly, in the German Daschner Case⁸³ an 11 year old boy was kidnapped by a law student, Magnus Gaefen who demanded a one million Euro ransom for the child's release. Gaefen was arrested when he went to pick up the ransom and after one day of unsuccessful interrogation, the Frankfurt Police Vice-President Wolfgang Daschner who was conducting the investigation threatened to use severe physical pressure if he continued to withhold information regarding the location of the child. Daschner considered this the only and last chance to find the victim and save his life. Upon the threat of physical pressure, Gaefen confessed that he had already murdered the boy and gave the police information as to the location of the body. Both Daschner and Gaefen were eventually prosecuted. While Gaefen was found guilty for extortionate abduction and murder and sentenced to life imprisonment, the police officer Daschner was also found guilty of coercion under section 230 of the German Penal Code, however, the court invoked the rare provision of section 59 and refrained from imposing a punishment on grounds that the overall assessment of the accused's conduct and personality did not demand a punishment.⁸⁴

Arguments put forward by those who supported the actions of Daschner is that, in the name of the 'fight against terrorism', the police and military ought to be allowed to act outside the law and the constitution, and utilize methods not seen since the Nazis ruled Germany in order to protect the lives of the innocent.⁸⁵ However, certain observations and conclusions can be drawn from the above cases as there have been several scholarly debates in Israel and Germany on the use of torture by security agencies of the State. Attempts have been made to distinguish between preventive (administrative) torture employed to obtain information that may be vital to prevent further crimes, and repressive torture which is employed to obtain evidence for the criminal trial. Also, there is discussion as to the ex-post criminal liability of the torturer as distinguished from the ex-ante legality of the methods employed by the torturer.⁸⁶ Since the September 2001 attacks in America, the justifications for the use of

⁸⁰ Robinson M., 'Connecting Human Rights, Human Development and Human Security' in Wilson Ashby (ed) *Human Rights in the War on Terror* (Cambridge University Press 2001) 309

⁸¹ Langericht District Court Frankfurt Judgment of 20 December 2004 reprinted in *Neue Juristische Wochenschrift* (hereinafter NJW) [2005] 692-696

⁸² Commission of enquiry into the Methods of Investigation of the General Security Service regarding Hostile Terrorist activity (English version reprinted in 1989 23 *Israeli Law Review*)

⁸³ *Supra*

⁸⁴ Kai A., 'May a State torture suspects to save the life of Innocent?' [2008] 6 *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 261-287

⁸⁵ Leicht J. 'The Daschner case and the rehabilitation of torture' [2004]

⁸⁶ Kai A., 'May a State torture suspects to save the life of Innocent?' [2008] 268

torture in exceptional circumstances have continued to rage despite the fact that there is an absolute international prohibition against torture. The prohibition against torture is absolute in the sense that no exceptional circumstances whatsoever, whether a state of war or a threat of war, internal political instability or any other public emergency, may be invoked as a justification for torture.⁸⁷

Again, in Nigeria the use of torture to obtain information is also prohibited by various domestic legislation.⁸⁸ Therefore, military forces cannot permit the use of torture without betraying its own principles and losing credibility at the international stage.⁸⁹ However, in certain exceptional circumstances, it has been argued that the use of torture may be the only option left in order to prevent a catastrophic event from occurring. This argument is illustrated in the Israeli ticking time bomb case where terrorists have planned an attack that is going to occur very soon leading to the deaths of a large population of the State, unless the authorities are able to obtain critical information from the terrorist suspect they have captured.⁹⁰ Judge Misha'el Heshin of Israel's Supreme Court had asked Attorney Andre Rosenthal, lawyer to Muhammad Hamdan to persuade the court on whether or not to permit the use of torture on a suspect who may have information relating to a bomb that is set to go off in two hours and in which it was impossible to get everyone out.⁹¹

In this type of cases, one school of thought has canvassed for exceptions to the prohibition against torture arguing that the prohibition does not cater for those situations in which police officers or security agents' only option is to rely on torture to avert a serious danger. The German Daschner case demonstrates this scenario. In these circumstances, this school of thought advocates that the torturer be exempted from punishment since he carried out the act as a matter of necessity in order to save lives.⁹² This exemption from liability will not be a blanket exculpation but would depend on the facts of each individual case.

However, it is submitted that the above cases seem to make a case for the use of torture against a terrorist suspect in order to obtain information and prevent the death of innocent civilians is more theoretical than real. In many cases the security agencies are rarely sure of the exact role a suspect played with regards to a purported hypothetical terrorist threat or whether the suspect in their custody really had anything to do with such threat or whether in fact, the threat is real. Therefore permitting the use of torture on a suspect is riddled with so many uncertainties which make it difficult to give blanket permission to the Military forces to torture individuals in the name of securing the State and preventing massive loss of lives and property.⁹³ Further, the information gotten through the use of torture is often unreliable. A tortured suspect is prone to saying anything in order to put a stop to his physical pain and discomfort. The motivation for the War in Iraq was based on evidence given by the al-Libi who was captured after 9/11 attacks and flown to Egypt under extraordinary rendition to be tortured for intelligence. Intelligence the CIA obtained through torture included assertions that Al-Qaeda were learning to make biological and nuclear weapons or weapons of mass destruction, in Iraq. This information was proved to be false; proving once again that

⁸⁷ See article 2 United Nations Convention Against Torture

⁸⁸ Section 36(11) Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999.

⁸⁹ Kai A., 'May a State torture suspects to save the life of Innocent?' [2008] 269

⁹⁰ Devlin J. 'Ticking time bomb and the justification of torture' [2012] <http://www.e-ir.info/2012/07/05/the-ticking-bomb-and-the-justification-of-torture/> accessed 28th November, 2022.

⁹¹ Langfür S. 'Answer to the judge: The ticking bomb and the license to torture' [1996] www.hartford-hwp.com/archives/51a/095.html accessed 28th November 2022

⁹² Kai A., 'May a State torture suspects to save the life of Innocent?' [2008] 289

⁹³ Ibid

intelligence obtained by use of torture is unreliable.⁹⁴ Therefore, caution must be applied on the reliability of such information not to mislead the military forces.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

While terrorism remains a significant threat to modern civilization and the enjoyment of human rights, democracy and peace, it must be said that the State and its agencies take care not to violate the very law they intend to protect by engaging in acts that deprive individuals their human rights. To do so would signify a return to barbarian and inevitably promote the spread of terror. However, counter terrorism measures must place the protection of human rights as one of its priority, and these rights include those of the suspects in custody of the security agencies. Any attempt to force an accused or individual in custody must be gravely frowned at. In *the State v. Olashehu Salawau*⁹⁵ the court held that the police have no authority to obtain a statement from an accused in their custody, having read him his rights and told him he is not obliged to say anything. The judges rules, though rules of practice, are designed to leave it open to the arrested person to say nothing and to prevent police officers from trying to get the arrested person to say anything.

Furthermore, the doctrine of exceptional circumstance under military forces in counter-terrorism operation must be defined and stated clearly when and how to invoke it under a serious security threat of a nation, while same be accommodated in our local legislations and not to be seen as mere military practices or convention of security agencies.

REFERENCES

- Arabamen O.A. and others 'The impact of Counter-Terrorism Laws on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms' [2015]3 *Akungba Law Journal*, 131
- Chin Leng Lim and Elias O. "Withdrawing from custom and the paradox of consensualism in international law' [2010] 21 *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law* 143-156
- Devlin J. 'Ticking time bomb and the justification of torture' [2012] <http://www.e-ir.info/2012/07/05/the-ticking-bomb-and-the-justification-of-torture/>
- Langfur S. 'Answer to the judge: The ticking bomb and the license to torture' [1996] www.hartford-hwp.com/archives/51a/095.html
- Memorandum from Jay S. Bybee, Assistant Attorney Gen., Office of Legal Counsel, U.S. Dept. of Justice, to Alberto R. Gonzales, Counsel to the president, Standards of Conduct for Interrogation under 18 United States Code 2340-A (Agu. 1, 2022) reprinted in the Torture Papers.
- Mokhtar A. 'Human rights obligations v. derogations: article 15 of the European convention on human rights' [2004]8 *International Journal of Human Rights* 67

⁹⁴ Devlin J. (2012) "Ticking time bomb and the justification of torture". <http://www.e-ir.info/2012/07/05/the-ticking-bomb-and-the-justification-of-torture/> accessed 28th November, 2022.

⁹⁵ SC. 11/2011

Moser P.T 'Torture Papers, Never Again-Guarantees of Non-repetition for the Torture Committed by the Bush Administration during the 'War on Terror' [2011] 8, 201

Scheinin M. and Vermeulen M. 'Unilateral Exceptions to International law: Systematic Legal Analysis and Critique of Doctrines that Seek to Deny or Reduce the Applicability of Human Rights Norms in the fight against Terrorism' [2010] 10

Szurlej Christina, 'Protecting Human Rights while Countering Terrorism a Decade after 9/11'[2011] *Essex Human Rights Review* 2.